

10th Qualitative and Quantitative Methods in Libraries International Conference (QQML2018)

22 - 25 MAY 2018, CHANIA, CRETE, GREECE

Yet another QQML Conference has successfully come to its end in Chania on May 25th, having brought together a wide interdisciplinary audience including but not limited to LIS experts, technologists, doctoral students, library professionals, researchers and educators from about 40 countries, all looking forward to share their experience and considerations around challenges and opportunities facing the library world today.

Among most discussed topics during content-rich plenary and parallel sessions were initial and continuing librarian training, open access and institutional repositories' policies, strategies and best practices, the New Management effects on library service quality, library response to the changing socio-demographic realities, sustainability and inclusivity, academic library impact and value assessment, LIS research trends and future perspectives, Information Literacy instruction design, implementation and evaluation and user studies.

Thanks to a well laid-out program successfully grouping together a vast array of papers in a way that facilitated cohesion, knowledge exchange and communication, participants were presented with a long series of case studies most relevant to many, if not all, of the librarian hats today and addressing from medical, to business, to school, to public and university library professionals.

University library related topics, ranging from theoretical approaches to surveys and applications, seemed to dominate the conference. Covering at least one third of all sessions, they reminding us of the academic library's epitomizing importance in supporting change and streamlining innovation and sustainable development in many different ways and through a variety of approaches as presented by library administrators and researchers that demonstrated the strong determination of the library community to pursue radical collaborations (INFONET, H.E.LI.N, INELI, LIFE, CROSSCULT projects) and groundbreaking methodologies in evaluating user experience, conducting research and Human Resource training (UX Café, KUBIC, TOPIC MAPS, Sentiment Analysis, GOSMART) away from worst/best case scenarios to alternative futures that could more adequately respond to today's changing social, educational and informational scenarios.

In the scenic Chania Cultural Center's grounds, and at both the main foyer on the ground floor and the poster gallery upstairs, lively discussions held in-between sessions revolved mainly around possible future partnerships framed within LIS network's effort to upgrade its role and at the same time enhance its contributions in both the community and the academy, demonstrating overall a strong willingness to connect, share and collaborate.

10th QQML Conference has undeniably been an influential experience that opened new research and practice avenues for many of the participants who putting aside their digital identities even for just a little while, made the most of this face-to-face communication opportunity appreciating the value and advantages of on-site participation and socializing especially at a time where librarians struggle to survive the ICT hegemony.

Rapporteur: Stavroula Sant-Geronikolou is a third-year PhD student of Library and Information Sciences at the University of Madrid-Charles III (UC3M), currently conducting a short-term research stay at the University of West Attica. She holds a BA in French Literature from the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, a Master's degree in Libraries and Digital Information Services (UC3M) and postgraduate certifications in Educational Technologies from Antonio de Nebrija University. Her thesis focuses on factors potentially impacting library use data capitalization prospects within Spanish and Greek Higher Education ecosystems. Her academic interests also include Information Literacy, Learning Commons, Creative Industries and High Impact Practices.

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4340-7463>